

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Production of methyl lactate with Sn-USY and Sn- β : insights into real hemicellulose valorization

Jose M. Jiménez-Martin, † Miriam El Tawil-Lucas, † Maia Montaña, † Maria Linares, † Amin

Osatiashtiani, ‡ Francisco M. Vila, ‡ David Martín Alonso, ‡ Jovita Moreno, † Alicia García, † and

*Jose Iglesias †, □, **

† Chemical & Environmental Engineering Group. Universidad Rey Juan Carlos. C/ Tulipan s/n, 28933. Madrid, Spain.

‡ Energy & Bioproducts Research Institute (EBRI), College of Engineering and Physical Sciences, Aston University, Aston Triangle, Birmingham B4 7ET, United Kingdom

‡ Energy and Sustainable Chemistry (EQS) Group. Institute of Catalysis and Petrochemistry, CSIC, C/ Marie Curie 2, Campus de Cantoblanco. 28049 Madrid, Spain

□ Instituto de Tecnologías para la Sostenibilidad. Universidad Rey Juan Carlos. C/ Tulipan s/n,
28933. Madrid, Spain.

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REACTANTS & REAGENTS

Commercial USY (CBV 712, Zeolyst International) and β (CP814C*, Zeolyst International) zeolites were used as parent materials for the synthesis of Sn-USY and Sn- β materials, respectively. Nitric acid (HNO₃, Sigma Aldrich, 70%) was used in the dealumination process. Methylene chloride (CH₂Cl₂, Scharlab), tin (IV) chloride pentahydrate (SnCl₄·5H₂O, 98%, Alfa Aesar), and triethylamine (N(CH₂CH₃)₃, NEt₃, 99%, Sigma Aldrich) were used in the metalation procedure as solvent, tin source, and grafting promoter, respectively. Potassium chloride (KCl, 99%, Sigma Aldrich) was used as alkaline cation source to produce [K]Sn-zeolites. D-(+)-glucose (GLU, 99%, Sigma Aldrich), D-(+)-mannose (MAN, 99%, Sigma Aldrich), D-(+)-xylose (XYL, 99%, Sigma Aldrich), L-(+)-arabinose (ARA, 98%, Sigma Aldrich), glycolaldehyde dimer (GLA, 99%, Sigma Aldrich) and dihydroxyacetone (DHA, 99%, Sigma Aldrich) were used in the catalytic performance test as substrates. Methanol (CH₃OH, HPLC Grade, Sharlab) and milli-Q grade deionized water were used in the catalytic performance tests as solvents. Methyl D-lactate (MLA, 99%, Sigma Aldrich), methyl glycolate (MG, 98%, Sigma Aldrich), methyl vinyl glycolate (MVG, 98.4%, Apollo Scientific), glycolaldehyde dimethyl acetal (GADMA, 98%, Alfa Aesar), methyl 2-hydroxy-4-methoxybutanoate (MMHB, 99%, BioSynth), methyl levulinate (MLE, 98%, Sigma Aldrich), methoxymethyl furfural (MMF, 95%, abcr GmbH) and 5-hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF, 98%, abcr GmbH) were used in the preparation of standards stock solutions for the calibration of the gas chromatography unit, using n-

decane (C₁₀H₂₂, 98%, Honeywell) as internal standard. D-(+)-glucose (GLU, 99%, Sigma Aldrich), D-(-)-fructose (FRU, 99%, Sigma Aldrich), D-(+)-mannose (MAN, 99%, Sigma Aldrich) and methyl-D-glucopyranoside (MGP, 99%, Sigma Aldrich) were used as standards for HPLC analysis. Pyridine (anhydrous, 99.8%, Sigma-Aldrich) and KBr (Spectroscopy grade, Fisher Chemical) were used in DRIFT spectroscopic studies.

TABLES

Table S1. Stoichiometric coefficients considered in the calculation of product yields –carbon basis– as a function of the starting substrate.

	Hexoses	Pentoses	DHA	Glycolaldehyde
MLA	2	1.66	1	0.66
MG	3	2.5	1.5	1
GADMA	3	2.5	1.5	1
MVG	1.5	1.25	0.75	0.5
MLE	1.2	1	0.6	0.4
MMHB	1.5	1.25	0.75	0.67
MMF	1	1.2	0.5	0.33
HMF	1	1.2	0.5	0.33
DHA	2	1.66	-	0.66
C6-glycosides	1	-	-	-
C5-glycosides	-	1	-	-

Table S2. Composition of hemicellulose hydrolysate recovered from different biomass sources as determined through NREL/TP-510-42623 standard. Extraction and recovery efficiencies for pentoses and hexoses.

Scots Pine			White Birch			Sugarcane Bagasse		
Carbohydrates	Conc. (%)		Carbohydrates	Conc. (%)		Carbohydrates	Conc. (%)	
Glucose	15.3		Glucose	5.1		Glucose	9.8	
Mannose	30.8		Mannose	2.9		Mannose	0.0	
Galactose	9.4		Galactose	5.9		Galactose	3.1	
Xylose	19.9		Xylose	69.6		Xylose	68.2	
Arabinose	8.1		Arabinose	3.2		Arabinose	8.0	
Oligomers C ₆	4.2		Oligomers C ₆	1.6		Oligomers C ₆	0.0	
Oligomers C ₅	8.1		Oligomers C ₅	11.6		Oligomers C ₅	15.7	
Extraction (%)	C ₅	86.5	Extraction (%)	C ₅	88.1	Extraction (%)	C ₅	93.1
	C ₆	88.0		C ₆	87.6		C ₆	76.9
Recovery (%)	C ₅	77.1	Yield (%)	C ₅	79.5	Yield (%)	C ₅	80.1
	C ₆	81.6		C ₆	87.5		C ₆	75.5

Different values between extraction and recovery are due to some C₅ sugars are extracted but converted into furfural and humins, and some C₆ sugars are extracted but converted into HMF, levulinic acid and humins.

Table S3. Impurities and their concentration found in GLV-organosolv Scots Pine hemicellulose hydrolysate.

		Scots Pine
Na	(mg·kg ⁻¹)	7.1
K	(mg·kg ⁻¹)	31.0
Ca	(mg·kg ⁻¹)	139.7
Mg	(mg·kg ⁻¹)	13.2
5-HMF	(g·L ⁻¹)	<0.01
GVL	(g·L ⁻¹)	<0.01

SUPPLEMENTARY SCHEMES AND FIGURES

Scheme S1. Reactions pathways taking place in the transformation of hemicellulose monosaccharides in methanol.

Scheme S2. Simplified scheme highlighting the principal transformations and products in the transformation of hemicellulose monosaccharides in the presence of [K]Sn-USY and [K]Sn-β zeolites in methanol media.

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(C) comparison for both Sn-USY and Sn- β catalyst.

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A-1

B-1

A-2

B-2

Figure S5. Thermogravimetric analysis of spent catalyst, Sn-USY (1) and Sn-β (2), after catalyst reuse in the transformation of mannose (A) and arabinose (B) in methanol.

Figure S7. Thermogravimetric analysis of spent catalyst, Sn-USY (1) and Sn- β (2), after catalyst reuse in the transformation of mannose (A) and arabinose (B) in methanol:water (96:4wt%) media.

Figure S8. ^{13}C (A) and ^1H (B) NMR spectra of Sn- β spent catalyst in the transformation of dihydroxyacetone (DHA) and glycolaldehyde (GLA) (black solid lines) and the liquid-extracted compounds after washing with CD_3Cl (solid red lines)